

Guide for Consultations on Coscine & Storage Space Applications

This guide is intended to serve as a basis and orientation aid for the content of counseling sessions (online or in person). The content was developed by the Coscine Service Management Team and the RDM staff of participating universities. Feedback and suggestions are welcome and can be sent to servicedesk@rwth-aachen.de in order to continuously improve the process.

Topic	Content & Helpful Links	Notes & Comments
Key Features of Coscine	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - General Information to Coscine - Script for Coscine Demonstration (see Appendix) - Coscine Tutorial Videos - Event Page for Workshops - Testprojects - Note: Coscine does not assign DOIs, but EPIC handle PIDs at project and file level! 	
Storage space request via Coscine-JARDS – General information	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Documentation - Flowchart for Resource Types <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Difference between metadata delivery via Web and S3 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Web: Mandatory metadata delivery via UI ▪ S3: No forced metadata entry via the UI, therefore this scope of application is necessary ▪ WORM resources (if required) - Explain the review process <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Time frame (2 weeks per reviewer) o Note: Information in the storage space application is visible to external reviewers! 	

<p>Storage space request via Coscine-JARDS - Fill out/support storage space request</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Selection Policy - Note: Once submitted, storage space requests cannot be edited! <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Option: RDM staff as PC for joint editing via Coscine-JARDS (may need to be adjusted before submission) - Is the storage of personal data required? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Refer to the university's data protection officer for clarification - Content-related aspects relevant to the storage space request: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o File types + quantity = requested storage space o Relevance of metadata o Metadata profiles (AIMS) o Workflow for data upload and metadata entry (reference to option for adding a PDF) - Indication of consultation in the storage space request 	
<p>Outlook</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - General open questions will be taken up by RDM staff during Coscine consultation hours or sent to servicedesk@rwth-aachen.de - Contribution to community features - Citation template for publications 	

Appendix: Script for a Coscine demonstration

Step-by-step instructions to assist you during a live demonstration of Coscine

Authors:

Ilona Lang (RWTH Aachen University) und Katja Jansen (RWTH Aachen University)

Date created:

21.05.2024

Last changes:

12.02.2026 (Version 1.2.0)

Abstract:

The script in this document describes a demonstration of Coscine for training courses or presentations. A detailed tour can take up to 15 minutes and should be practiced beforehand. Depending on the time frame, the tour can be shortened. **Areas marked in yellow should be emphasized in accordance with the FAIR principles.**

This document does not replace the documentation, FAQs, or attendance at a training course (see <https://www.coscine.de/>). A thorough understanding of Coscine's functions should be acquired before giving a tour. Changes/comments may be added at any time via “Track Changes.”

Contact:

If you have any questions about this document (that cannot be answered by the documentation/FAQ), please write to servicedesk@rwth-aachen.de.

Preparation:

Use one of the five test projects from your own university and have sample files ready to upload. If you do not have access to your university's test projects, contact the RDM staff at your university or create a project yourself.

Please note: Every two weeks on Tuesday mornings, the development team performs a live deployment. In addition, interim deployments may occur in urgent cases. To ensure smooth accessibility of the Coscine platform during the live demonstration, please contact coscine.servicemanagement@itc.rwth-aachen.de in good time (at least one week in advance).

Recommendations for a „good“ test project:

- Create 1-2 additional subprojects
- At least 2 member types: Owner, Member (optional: Guest)
 - **Attention!** Names and, if applicable, email addresses will be shown during the presentation; obtain consent in advance if necessary
 - Optional: at least 1 member from another university
- All resource types including quota available (at least Web, S3, Linked Data, GitLab)
 - Helpful: resource type in the name (GitLab test, Web test, etc.)
 - Web resource: preferably with RADAR profile so that file uploads are fast during the tour (no need to fill out 10 fields first...)
 - S3 resource: data uploaded via S3 client and without metadata description (necessary to show the difference to web resources)

Step-by-step instructions

1. Start: <https://www.coscine.de/>

2. Login

- Via Institutional Account
 - a. Optional: Logout & Login via ORCID

3. Show Home-Surface

- Optional: Change Language due to audience

4. Open User Profile

- General Information
 - a. **ORCID Login:** For external participants, note that information must be added late
 - b. After Login: Verification of E-Mail needed (E-Mail with Link)
- Access Tokens (Creation for Access via API)
- User preferences
 - a. Language selection
 - b. Notification management
 - c. **Connected accounts (recommended!)**
 - d. Option for deletion of account

5. Show project

- Explanation for project settings (**1st mandatory metadata level**)
 - a. Declaration for metadata visibility: Public ≠ Public at the Internet data level
- Show member management
 - a. Adding users: by user (enter at least the first three letters of the name or the email address)
 - b. Explain import function
 - c. Role management (owner, member, and guest)
 - i. Owner = can see everything, can edit everything
 - ii. Member = cannot edit project settings, but has write access to data
 - iii. Guest = has read-only access
 - d. Manage quota: skip, explain resources first
- Indicate the possibility of subprojects (separate project unit)
 - a. Owners can be automatically transferred from the main project (default setting)

6. Creation of a new resource

- General:

- a. For audiences with quota rights (= [participating organization](#)): Select web resource
 - b. For audiences without quota rights: Select linked data resource
- Explain resource settings (**2nd mandatory metadata level**)
 - a. Select metadata profile depending on audience (e.g., EngMeta as defined schema) (**3rd mandatory metadata level**)
 - b. Show options for customizing a metadata profile without AIMS: fix term, hide term, etc.
 - c. Optional: Excursus on AIMS (click on “Create” and show AIMS interface, refer to documentation)
 - d. Explain **license**: optional, but important information for other project members
 - e. Show overview (ideally, do not confirm, but switch to prepared resource)

7. Open resource

- Select a file and show metadata
- Upload a new file
 - a. Demonstrate metadata entry (note that there is no upload option before metadata entry)
 - Edit resource
 - a. Show **PID**, copy URL, and resolve
 - b. Metadata profile name → increased reusability
 - c. Actions “Archive,” “Delete,” “Local metadata copy”
- Quota management
 - a. Show web settings
 - b. Explain “Request more”
 - c. Optional (depending on time): Show other resource types
 - i. S3 resources with missing metadata – note on “bypassing” the upload block – therefore more complex application for quota via Coscine-JARDS platform (metadata management must be secured in advance)
 - ii. Linked data for data outside DataStorage.nrw/GitLab
 - iii. GitLab for code
- Show **search function**
 - a. Search for “Test,” for example (set display settings to “50” at the bottom right)
- Show feature for data publication requests
 - a. Coscine ≠ publication platform
 - b. Addition of further data publication services planned for the future